

Validation of the System Split Application through Sandbox Testing

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SUMMARY

This paper presents the sandbox-based testing and validation of the System Split application developed within the Horizon Europe project Reliability, Resilience and Defense Technology for the Grid (R²D²). The System Split module is designed to detect system split events and support coordinated restoration actions among Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and the Regional Coordination Centre (RCC).

The sandbox environment provides a fully isolated framework that enables safe execution, debugging, and performance testing of the application under realistic operating conditions. Within this environment, system split detection algorithms and coordination procedures can be repeatedly tested and verified without any impact on production SCADA/EMS systems.

The results confirm that the sandbox approach improves testing efficiency, enhances reliability, and provides a secure platform for continuous validation and deployment of real-time control center applications.

KEYWORDS

sandbox, system split, software testing, SCADA/EMS, resilience

1. INTRODUCTION

Enhancing the resilience and reliability of power system operation has become one of the key priorities of the European energy sector, particularly in the context of increasing system complexity, higher penetration of renewable energy sources, and strengthened cross-border interconnections. Large synchronous areas, such as the Continental Europe synchronous area, require a high level of coordination among Transmission System Operators (TSOs), especially during emergency conditions that may lead to loss of synchronism or system separation.

Recent large-scale system split events, notably those recorded in 2006 and 2021, as well as other recent disturbances in the European power system, have highlighted the challenges associated with real-time operation and regional coordination during severe system disturbances. These events demonstrated that, although operational rules and procedures are well defined at the European level, their practical application under time-critical conditions is highly demanding. System operators are required to rapidly assess the situation, identify affected areas, and coordinate actions with neighboring TSOs and Regional Coordination Centres (RCCs), often under significant uncertainty and time pressure.

To support system operators in addressing these challenges, the System Split application was developed as part of the IRIS (Resilience Suite for TSO and DSO) product within the Horizon Europe R²D² project [1]. The main objective of this application is to automatically detect system separation events using real-time measurements and network topology information, and to initiate structured coordination processes among involved stakeholders. The application guides operators through predefined operational steps aligned with the ENTSO-E Emergency and Restoration procedures, thereby supporting consistent and coordinated response during system split scenarios.

The initial version of the System Split application was validated in an offline study environment, where functional behavior was assessed using predefined network models and offline disturbance scenarios. While this approach enabled verification of the core detection and coordination logic, it did not fully capture the characteristics of a real operational environment, particularly with respect to real-time data exchange, system integration, and operational constraints.

In the current development phase, validation of the System Split application is performed using a scenario-based testing approach within a sandbox environment. Representative system split scenarios are defined by simulating outages of power system equipment that are expected to result in the formation of electrical islands. These scenarios are executed end-to-end in an isolated virtual infrastructure that mirrors the operational setup of the Security Coordination Centre (SCC), enabling realistic evaluation of both detection and coordination behavior.

This scenario-based sandbox validation approach allows systematic assessment of the application's functionality, robustness, and operational suitability without introducing risks to production SCADA/EMS systems. By executing predefined disturbance scenarios and observing the resulting application behavior, the validation implicitly covers detection logic, coordination workflows, and operator interaction under controlled and repeatable conditions.

The following sections of the paper provide an overview of the System Split application and its core functionalities, describe the sandbox environment and its integration with SCADA/EMS systems, and present the results obtained through representative scenario-based

validation tests. The paper concludes with a discussion of the main findings and their relevance for real-time system operation.

2. SYSTEM SPLIT APPLICATION OVERVIEW

The System Split application is designed to support real-time detection and coordinated handling of power system separation events within large interconnected transmission networks. Its primary objective is to enhance situational awareness and coordination efficiency during emergency conditions by combining automated detection mechanisms with structured operator guidance compliant with ENTSO-E Emergency and Restoration procedures.[2]

From a functional perspective, the application operates as an integrated component of the SCADA/EMS environment and continuously processes real-time system data. As illustrated in Figure 1, the core inputs to the application include SCADA/EMS telemetry and switching device statuses, as well as frequency measurements obtained from wide-area monitoring systems (WAMS) and Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs). These data streams are processed by the Network Topology Processor (NTP), which maintains an up-to-date representation of system connectivity and identifies electrical islands based on breaker statuses and equipment connectivity. [3]

The system split detection logic builds upon this topological analysis by incorporating frequency-based verification. Frequency measurements are used to validate whether newly identified islands operate asynchronously or exhibit significant frequency deviations, thereby increasing the robustness of split detection and reducing the likelihood of false alarms caused by incomplete topology models or erroneous telemetry. This combined approach enables reliable identification of system split events under real-time operational conditions.

Once a system split event is validated and confirmed, the application transitions from detection to coordination support mode. At this stage, the focus shifts from identifying the disturbance to supporting coordinated operational response across affected system areas. The coordination logic module, as part of the overall architecture, is responsible for managing this transition and orchestrating subsequent actions via a dedicated operator interface and a coordination platform implemented using OperatorFabric (OF) technology.[4]

The coordination workflow supported by the application is illustrated in Figure 1. Following detection, the application first identifies the Transmission System Operators directly affected by the system split. This information is derived from the network topology and island boundaries and is presented to operators in a structured and unambiguous manner. Acknowledgement and confirmation steps ensure that all relevant parties share a consistent understanding of the system state.

Subsequently, the application supports coordination of frequency control actions within the separated system areas. In accordance with ENTSO-E rules, this includes assistance in managing frequency containment and restoration processes and in coordinating actions between TSOs and the Regional Coordination Centre (RCC). The application facilitates nomination of frequency and resynchronization leaders, ensuring that responsibilities are clearly assigned and communicated during the restoration process.

Resynchronization steps represent the final phase of the coordination workflow. The application provides guidance and status tracking throughout this phase, supporting orderly

restoration of synchronism between system areas once technical and operational conditions are fulfilled. Throughout the entire process, the coordination platform enables structured communication, logging of actions, and transparency of decisions, while keeping system operators firmly in the decision-making loop.

A key design principle of the System Split application is that it acts as a decision-support tool rather than an autonomous control system. All critical operational decisions remain under operator authority, with the application providing timely information, procedural guidance, and coordination support. This approach ensures compatibility with existing operational practices, regulatory requirements, and the operational responsibilities of TSOs and RCCs.

By integrating real-time detection, robust verification, and structured coordination workflows, the System Split application addresses key challenges associated with large-scale system split events. Its architecture and functionality, as presented in Figures 1, form the basis for systematic validation within a sandbox environment, which is described in the following section.

Figure 1. System Split Application Architecture and Coordination Workflow

3. SANDBOX ENVIRONMENT

3.1 Purpose of the Sandbox Environment

Sandbox environments are widely used in critical software systems to enable safe testing, validation, and evolution of complex applications without affecting production operation. In general, a sandbox represents an isolated execution environment that replicates key characteristics of the target operational system, while preventing unintended interactions with live infrastructure. Such environments are particularly valuable in domains where software failures or misbehavior could lead to significant operational or safety risks.

In the context of power system operation, and especially within SCADA/EMS environments, the use of sandbox environments is of particular importance. Real-time applications interact with large volumes of continuously changing data, depend on complex system configurations, and are tightly integrated with operational processes. Testing such applications directly in production environments is typically infeasible, as even minor errors may result in incorrect operator guidance, loss of situational awareness, or unintended operational actions.

For the System Split application, these challenges are further amplified by the critical nature of the addressed events. System split scenarios are rare but high-impact disturbances that require fast, coordinated, and accurate response across multiple control centers. Validation of detection logic, coordination workflows, and operator interaction must therefore be performed under conditions that are as realistic as possible, while maintaining complete isolation from live operational systems.

The sandbox environment introduced in this work serves precisely this purpose. It provides a controlled virtual infrastructure in which the complete System Split application can be executed end-to-end, including topology processing, frequency-based verification, and coordination workflows. At the same time, strict isolation ensures that no data, commands, or side effects can propagate to production SCADA/EMS systems.

Beyond functional testing, the sandbox environment enables evaluation of additional non-functional aspects that are critical for real-time operation. These include performance under stress conditions, behavior during incomplete or inconsistent data scenarios, and resilience against cybersecurity threats. The ability to repeatedly execute identical test scenarios also supports systematic regression testing as the application evolves.

In summary, the sandbox environment represents a key enabler for reliable validation and continuous improvement of the System Split application. By combining realism with isolation, it allows comprehensive testing of both technical functionality and operational workflows, ensuring that the application can be confidently deployed and maintained in mission-critical control center environments. This approach is particularly important for applications supporting ENTSO-E Emergency and Restoration processes, where validation under realistic conditions is essential.

3.2 Sandbox Architecture

The sandbox environment is implemented as a fully isolated virtual infrastructure designed to closely replicate the operational setup of the Security Coordination Centre (SCC) control environment. Its primary architectural objective is to provide a realistic execution context for the System Split application, while ensuring strict separation from production SCADA/EMS systems and operational networks. The architecture is designed to replicate key characteristics of the operational SCC environment while enabling controlled and repeatable testing.

From an architectural standpoint, the sandbox follows a layered and modular design. Core components of the System Split application, such as the Network Topology Processor, system split detection logic, coordination logic, and operator interface, are deployed on dedicated virtual machines, depending on deployment requirements. This approach enables controlled execution, simplified configuration management, and independent lifecycle management of individual software components as summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. Overview of the Network Architecture of the SCC Environment

Table 1 – Virtualized server infrastructure of the sandbox environment

Server Name	Function	Operating System
Virtualized SCADA Server	Hosts the SCADA application and provides real-time measurements and system status data	CentOS Linux 7.x
SCADA Replication “Jump” Server	Secure gateway used for controlled data transfer between security zones and replication of SCADA data	CentOS Linux 7.x
Virtualized R ² D ² Application Server	Executes the System Split application and related processing services	Oracle Linux 9.x
Virtualized OperatorFabric Server	Hosts the coordination platform used for communication between TSOs and RCC	Oracle Linux 9.x
Virtualized Archive Server	Stores historical SCADA data and archived operational information	CentOS Linux 7.x
Virtualized R ² D ² Test Application Server	Sandbox instance used for testing and validation of the System Split application	Oracle Linux 9.x

Virtualized OperatorFabric Test Server	Sandbox instance used for testing the coordination platform	Oracle Linux 9.x
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The sandbox environment reproduces the main data flows present in the operational system, as illustrated in Figure 2. SCADA/EMS telemetry, switching device statuses, and configuration data are provided to the sandbox through replicated or replayed data sources. These data sources are derived from historical recordings or synthetically generated to represent realistic operational scenarios. Frequency measurements from WAMS or PMU-based systems are integrated in a similar manner, enabling consistent testing of frequency-based verification mechanisms without reliance on live measurement streams. Data transfer strictly follows a unidirectional pattern from the SCADA/EMS domain toward the application layer, ensuring that no control commands or feedback can be issued toward the operational system. This ensures strict decoupling between operational systems and the application layer.

Isolation between the sandbox and production environments is enforced at multiple levels. Network segmentation and firewall rules prevent any bidirectional communication with operational systems, ensuring that sandbox activities cannot influence real-time operation. At the application level, all interfaces are configured in read-only or simulation modes, further eliminating the possibility of unintended control actions. This multi-layer isolation strategy allows safe execution of complex and potentially disruptive test scenarios. The System Split application operates as a decision-support module, fully decoupled from SCADA/EMS control functions.

The sandbox architecture also supports flexible scenario management. Network models, configuration parameters, and test inputs can be modified without impacting other components, allowing systematic evaluation of different system split conditions and coordination sequences. This flexibility is essential for testing rare but critical events that cannot be safely reproduced in production systems.

In addition, the sandbox environment is designed to support observability and traceability of application behavior. Detailed logging, event tracking, and monitoring mechanisms are enabled across all components, allowing post-analysis of detection decisions, coordination steps, and operator interactions. This capability is particularly valuable for validating compliance with ENTSO-E procedures and for identifying potential improvements in application logic or user interaction.

Overall, the sandbox architecture provides a realistic yet fully controlled execution environment for the System Split application. By closely mirroring the operational SCC architecture while maintaining strict isolation, it forms a robust foundation for systematic validation, iterative development, and future extension of the application.

4. TEST SCENARIOS AND VALIDATION RESULTS

Validation of the System Split application was performed using a scenario-based testing approach within the sandbox environment described in Section 3. The validation focused on representative system split scenarios designed to reflect realistic operational conditions in large interconnected transmission networks.

The validation aimed to assess the following key aspects: (i) correctness of system split detection, (ii) robustness under imperfect data conditions, (iii) proper execution of coordination workflows, and (iv) consistency of operator interaction.

The expected outcomes of the validation included accurate identification of electrical islands, absence of false detections, correct sequencing of coordination steps, and successful completion of the resynchronization process. All scenarios were executed in a controlled and repeatable manner, ensuring consistency of validation results and enabling reliable assessment of application behavior.

Scenarios were defined based on the simulated outage of selected power system elements whose disconnection was expected to result in the formation of electrical islands. These outages were chosen to represent credible contingency situations that could occur during real system operation. All scenarios were executed end-to-end within the sandbox environment, allowing controlled observation of the complete application workflow.

System split was simulated using the SCADA model of the regional South East Europe (SEE) network. In the examined scenario, the southern and eastern parts of the Serbian network separated from the regional SEE network, forming three islands: Island 1 – the major part of the regional SEE network, Island 2 – consisting of the southern part of Serbia’s transmission network (EMS) and parts of North Macedonia’s transmission network (MEPSO); and Island 3 – consisting of the eastern part of Serbia’s transmission network and parts of Bulgaria’s (ESO) and Romania’s transmission networks (TEL). The splitting lines are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Separation of the regional network into three electrical islands

Dashed lines present splitting lines, while numbers refer to created islands. In order to separate Island 2 located in the southern part of the Serbian transmission network and marked by a yellow dashed line, the transmission lines listed in Table 2 were disconnected. Island 3, located in the eastern part of the Serbian transmission network and marked by an orange dashed line, was formed by disconnecting the lines listed in Table 3. Based on Figure 3, Table 2 and Table 3, it can be concluded that the splitting lines extended predominantly through the Serbian transmission system, with only smaller sections extending into the neighbouring transmission systems.

Table 2. Disconnected transmission lines for creation of Island 1 and Island 2

No	Line	Voltage level	TSO
1	Niš 2 – Leskovac 2	400kV	EMS
2	Niš 2 – Leskovac 2	110kV	EMS
3	Niš 2 – Niš 15	110kV	EMS
4	Štip – Ch. Mogila	400kV	MEPSO/ ESO
5	Skoplje 5 – Uroševac	400kV	MEPSO/ KOSTT
6	Bitola – Florina	400kV	MEPSO/ IPTO
7	Dubrovo – Solun	400kV	MEPSO/ IPTO

Table 3. Disconnected transmission lines for creation of Island 3

No	Line	Voltage level	TSO
1	Đerdap – Drmno	400kV	EMS
2	Petrovac – Neresnica	110kV	EMS
3	Petrovac – Bor 1	110kV	EMS
4	Jagodina 4 – Niš 2	400kV	EMS
5	Kruševac 1 – Niš 2	220kV	EMS
6	Kosovo B – Niš 2	400kV	KOSTT/ EMS
7	Prokuplje – Niš 2	110kV	EMS
8	Niš 1 – Niš 8	110kV	EMS
9	Niš 1 – Niš 2	110kV	EMS
10	Niš 2 – Sofia Zapad	400kV	EMS/ ESO
11	Đerdap – Potile de Fier	400kV	EMS/ TEL

For the executed scenario, the expected outcome was the detection of system separation and initiation of the corresponding coordination process.

In the tested scenario, the System Split application successfully detected the formation of electrical islands based on topological analysis supported by frequency-based verification. The application correctly identified island boundaries and classified the events as system split conditions, with no missed detections or false positives observed during testing.

Following successful detection, the application automatically initiated the predefined coordination workflow. All coordination steps were executed in the expected sequence, including identification of affected TSOs within the observability zone and progression through the defined coordination phases. Operator interaction through the coordination platform was consistent with the designed workflows, and all coordination steps were completed successfully.

It is important to note that, in this coordination process, some cards are created manually by the RCC (acting as the coordination process leader), while others are automatically generated by the Coordination Platform. The approach to card creation, along with the TSO’s response, remains consistent, while the information may vary depending on the coordination stage.

Information about system split is exchanged between the NTP and the Coordination Platform in the form of an XML file, which content is then processed and used for the automatic creation of several cards within the coordination platform, including the first one in the coordination

process. This initial card was sent to all coordination participants (TSOs from the SEE region and SCC as RCC), as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Card with information about system split detection

The card shown in Figure 4 contains basic information about the system split detected by NTP, the number of islands and the participating TSOs for each island.

Following the initial notification of the system split, further coordination between TSOs and RCC is required including coordination via teleconference. It is also necessary for TSOs to confirm their status as directly affected TSOs, which is automatically determined based on information provided by NTP. TSO users are requested to confirm their status regarding the system separation line.

The newly formed islands are unbalanced: depending on the pre-split active power flows across the separation lines, certain islands exhibit a surplus of generation (positive imbalance), while others face a generation deficit (negative imbalance). NTP, regarding this, also has a role in computing the imbalance for each island and, based on these values together with Load Frequency Control (LFC) parameters, generates proposals for remedial actions to support frequency stabilization and accelerate restoration towards nominal values.

Several automated cards were generated to inform TSOs about mandatory actions prior to the Frequency Leader (FL) nomination, about TSO LFC capabilities per island, and, based on this information, about the proposed FL for each island. The proposed FL for each island is the TSO with the highest LFC value. As the LFC value is the highest for EMS TSO in all three detected islands, EMS TSO is proposed as the FL for all three islands.

The next coordination steps are about the resynchronization of islands. In this demonstration case, Island 1 and Island 3 were selected for resynchronization first. Since EMS is the FL for both islands, EMS is chosen as the Resynchronization Leader (RL) and this is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Resynchronization Leader – Information and Confirmation

Following the resynchronization of Island 1 and Island 3, the NTP detected a change in the network state: two islands are now present. Automatically generated new card is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. System Split detection – Warning and Confirmation – 2 Islands

The coordination process is performed in the same manner as in the situation with three detected islands. After determining the directly affected TSOs, the NTP proposed remedial actions to accelerate the restoration of normal frequency. Imbalances and remedial actions are calculated by the NTP.

Following successful resynchronization, all TSOs are informed via a dedicated informative card (see Figure 7) and requested to return their frequency controllers to normal operational mode.

Figure 7. Executed resynchronization – Warning and Confirmation

The obtained results demonstrate a clear correspondence between defined test scenarios and observed application behavior, confirming reliable and consistent operation under realistic system split conditions and supporting the suitability of the System Split application for real-time operational deployment.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comprehensive validation of the System Split application through a sandbox-based testing approach tailored for real-time SCADA/EMS environments. The application addresses one of the most critical operational challenges in large interconnected power systems by providing automatic detection of system separation events and structured coordination support in accordance with ENTSO-E Emergency and Restoration procedures.

The proposed sandbox environment enables repeatable, risk-free, and realistic validation of the complete System Split workflow, including topology processing, frequency-based verification, and coordination logic. By closely mirroring the operational architecture of the Security Coordination Centre (SCC) while maintaining strict isolation from production systems, the sandbox provides a realistic execution context suitable for testing rare but high-impact system split scenarios that cannot be safely reproduced in live environments. The validation confirmed correct system split detection, absence of false positives, and consistent execution of coordination workflows across all tested scenarios.

The results confirm that the sandbox-based approach is effective not only for functional verification, but also for evaluating non-functional aspects such as performance, robustness, and cybersecurity constraints. This significantly increases confidence in the readiness of the

System Split application for deployment and long-term operation in real-time control center environments.

Beyond validation, the sandbox represents an important step toward a digital twin of the operational power system environment. By combining network models, measurement data, and operational workflows, it provides a foundation for advanced analysis, operator training, and predictive studies.

The presented results demonstrate a practical and reliable validation approach for both detection and coordination functionalities prior to deployment in mission-critical SCADA/EMS environments. This approach contributes to bridging the gap between offline studies and real-time operation, providing a foundation for safer deployment of advanced decision-support applications in control center environments, and can be readily extended to other emergency and restoration applications within SCADA/EMS environments.

Future work will focus on extending the sandbox framework to support additional emergency and restoration scenarios, further automation of test execution and result analysis, and deeper integration with continuous integration and deployment pipelines. In parallel, the evolution of the sandbox toward a digital twin-based validation environment will be explored, with the objective of further enhancing system resilience, operator preparedness, and coordination efficiency.

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